

ADAPTIVE QoS CENTRIC SERVICE ORIENT DYNAMIC CRYPTOGRAPHY TECHNIQUE FOR IMPROVED SECURITY IN CLOUD ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract

The problem of data security in cloud environment has been well studied. There exist numerous techniques to handle this issue. Some of the methods perform data encryption according to the profile of user, data nature etc. However, the security of such algorithms is not tampered proof and subject to compromise on guessing attacks. This affects the performance of such security algorithms. To handle this, a novel cryptographic scheme is presented in this article. The Adaptive QoS centric service orient dynamic cryptography (AQSDC) approach focuses on improving data security in the service orient environment. The method handles the client request and finds the data being accessed by the service request. Further, the service nature and the environmental and external network conditions are monitored and considered. According to the factors of various internal, external network conditions and service metrics, the method computes different crypto support measures like Crypto Traffic Class Support (CTCS), Crypto Throughput Class Support (CThCS), Crypto Tamper Class Support (CTaCS) and Crypto Data Class Support (CDCS). Using these measures, the method computes the sensitivity factor (SF) for the data being accessed. Accordingly, the method selects the class of algorithm to be used. Such algorithm from the selected class was used to split the service data into chunks and perform Class Centric Data Encryption (CCDE) algorithm which generates number of cipher blocks in a dynamic way. Generated blocks were reframed by the receiver for decryption. The proposed method improves the performance of data security with higher data encryption and decryption performance.

Index Terms: Cipher Systems, Cryptography, Service Classes, Data Class, Data Encryption Decryption, AQSDC, CCDE, QoS.

1. INTRODUCTION

Growth of information technology has opened the gate for the human society to perform variety of operations on the fly without considering the location where they are. Such facilities have been used by the human society for almost everything in their day-to-day activity. But in reality, the facilities provided by the technology also open the threats to be arrived to their step. As the human society accesses various services through their computers, laptops, mobile phones. The organizations provide various services for their users to access them to perform variety of task. As most of the processes are performed through accessing the services, the malicious users and adversaries launches various threats towards the service points.

Such threats are focused on damaging the request data or service data which in turn would affect the performance of any service orient environment. There are number of threats can be named which targets the service orient environment. They greatly focused on affecting the service performance, throughput performance and in total to degrade the QoS performance of the entire system.

Many threats can be named towards service orient environment like eavesdrop which blindly drop the service packets to degrade the through performance of any environment. Similarly, modification attack focused on reducing the throughput of service as well as environment. On the other side, tampering attacks are focused on modifying a part of data which makes the service data meaningless. For example, when a malicious user makes modification attack on a banking data by simply modifying the destination account to which the fund should be transferred, then the transaction become wrong. So, all these increases the requirement of maintaining the data security in various organizations.

The data security can be enforced in two ways, either by restricting the user from accessing the service, on the other side, by using efficient encryption schemes to make the system rigid against malicious users. We focus on the second, by enforcing rigid encryption schemes. In literature there exist several encryption algorithms available. They can be classified as symmetric and asymmetric schemes. Also, they can be classified as public and private key based approaches. However, there are many popular algorithms exist in literature as AES, RSA, Diffie Helman, MD5, HS4, ECC and so on.

The algorithms differ with the kind of key being used and the size. Both the kind of key and size of key makes big difference in terms of achieving security and time complexity. For example, the AES and RSA algorithms are less time complexity where ECC takes higher time. On the other side, ECC uses small size key where the rest takes higher sized keys which challenges the space complexity. So, the methods are not suitable for the service orient environment.

In recent times, the policy-based encryption schemes are arrived which uses different policies and based on that selection of key has been performed. Also attribute based encryption (ABE) has been used in service orient environment which uses different schemes and keys for different attributes. Still, the methods suffer to achieve expected performance in the data security.

Even though there exist several modern schemes to support the service orient environment, they suffer to achieve higher Quality of Service parameters like throughput, service throughput, latency, and data security. By considering all this, this article presents a novel Adaptive QoS centric Service Orient Dynamic Cryptography (AQSDC) approach. The method has been designed to handle service requests and choose the encryption scheme according to the QoS constraints of the environment and support to achieve higher performance in QoS metrics. The detailed approach has been presented in this section.

2. RELATED WORKS

There exist numerous techniques to handle security threats on service orient environment. Such methods are listed and discussed in this section.

EncryScation: A novel framework for cloud IaaS, DaaS security using encryption and Obfuscation techniques [1], presents two techniques, that is: Encryption, authentication at client side as well as Data Obfuscation at server side. Encryption helps user to provide secrecy to its data when it is transferred in the network.

Enhanced data storage security in cloud environment using encryption, compression and splitting technique [2], e proposed the concept of cloud data storage security strategy capable to overcome the shortcomings of traditional data protection algorithms and improving security using steganography, encryption decryption techniques, compression and splitting technique adoptable to better security for the cloud. We have developed a desktop application through which user can share data. This paper enhanced advance security goal for cloud data storage.

A multilevel encryption technique in cloud security [3], proposed a multilevel security scheme which is more secure than any type of single level encryption. Particularly our technique shows that only authorized user can able to access the cloud data. Our algorithm is fast and safe in both direction such as upload and download of a file. As decryption technique is multilevel so if some data is lost then it is very difficult to decrypt the data.

Enhancement of security mechanism for confidential data using AES-128, 192 and 256bit encryption in cloud [4], provide security major companies are using Advance Encryption Standard (AES) encryption technology. AES is using mainly 3 types of encryption keys: 128bit key encryption, 192bit key encryption and 256bit key encryption which are using 10, 12 and 14 iterations respectively. All these are using the plain text block of size 128bit. In proposed architecture, the cloud user will be facilitated with all the 3 encryption techniques 128, 192 and 256bits to choose and based on the size of the data the encryption process can be done.

Performance analysis of various encryption algorithms for usage in multistage encryption for securing data in cloud [5], Cloud computing is an emerging technology has grown a lot for virtualization and provides many services over the internet such as software as a service, platform as a service, infrastructure as a service and many more services which reduce the cost expenses and operating expenses. Now by using these services, data can store online in the cloud, then automatically a security concern will arise about data. Many protection techniques have been proposed till now. The best options available is encrypting the data before storing in third party cloud database and again decrypt the data after retrieving from the cloud.

Framework for client-side AES encryption technique in cloud computing [6], proposed user authentication to secure data of encryption algorithm with in cloud computing. Cloud computing allows users to use browser without application installation and access their

data at any computer using browser. This infrastructure guaranteed to secure the information in cloud server.

Cloud data security with hybrid symmetric encryption [7], proposed a new security model which utilizes the concept of hybrid encryption and decryption to provide a secure and protected environment for cloud data storage. In the proposed model, data owner (DO) outsources the encrypted data at cloud server to make it hidden from intruder and provide only authorized user with the corresponding decryption key to retrieve the original data. Use of hybrid encryption makes the data more protected from any malicious activity and provide a sound and secure system. During encryption or decryption process the concept of symmetric key cryptography is utilize as it is more efficient and faster than public key cryptography.

Enhancing the security of user data using the keyword encryption and hybrid cryptographic algorithm in cloud [8], proposed a novel identity-based hybrid encryption (RSA with ECC) to enhance the security of outsourced data. In this approach sender encrypts the sensitive data using hybrid algorithm. Then the proxy re encryption is used to encrypt the keyword and identity in standardize toward enrichment security of data.

Comparative study of homomorphic encryption methods for secured data operations in cloud computing [9], Providing security to the data involves network security, strategies of control and access to the service, storage of data. In spite of the service providers' effort to ensure trust among the clients for the security of data, there is lack of enthusiasm among the users to use the technology to its fullest capability. Homomorphic encryption is a way of providing security to the data in which operations can be done on encrypted data itself.

Enhanced encryption algorithm (EEA) for protecting users' credentials in public cloud [10], proposes an Enhanced Encryption Algorithm (EEA) for securing the data in cloud storage. This is a symmetric encryption algorithm. It uses same key for encrypting and decrypting the data before stored in to cloud. Result of the proposed EEA produces different ciphertext for same plaintext. It confuses the cryptanalyst (hackers) to get the original data. Hence this EEA is efficient hiding techniques for public cloud.

Cloud-EI Gamal: An efficient homomorphic encryption scheme [11], However, the fear of seeing sensitive data be processed in clear has become a major barrier to cloud services adoption. Indeed, researchers have stressed a useful technique called "homomorphic encryption", this technique allows specific type of computations to be performed on encrypted data without decrypting it the encryption schemes that support homomorphic properties are numerous; unfortunately, many attacks make these schemes insecure, especially when adopting these schemes to protect the confidentiality of outsourced data into the cloud due to the longtime of storing the ciphertexts by the same key.

Privacy preserving in TPA for secure cloud by using encryption technique [12], to achieve the privacy preserving public for auditing, we intended an explanation for TPA using three-way handshaking protocol through the Extensible Authentication Protocol (EAP) with

liberated encryption standard. Appropriately, from the cloud, we use the Verify Proof execute by TPA to audit to certify. In addition to this mechanism, the identity of each segment in the shared data is kept private from the public verifiers. Moreover, rather than verifying the auditing task one by one, this will capable to perform, the various auditing tasks simultaneously.

A hybrid data encryption technique using RSA and Blowfish for cloud computing on FPGAs [13], a hybrid Cryptosystem using RSA and Blowfish algorithm. This hybrid cryptosystem is Considered for cloud computing where digital signature is must for user authentication. So, this technique provides features of both symmetric and asymmetric cryptography. Also, blowfish is unpatented, so this cryptosystem is also cost efficient.

Use of Digital Signature with Diffie Hellman Key Exchange and AES Encryption Algorithm to Enhance Data Security in Cloud Computing [14], proposed to make use of digital signature and Diffie Hellman key exchange blended with (AES) Advanced Encryption Standard encryption algorithm to protect confidentiality of data stored in cloud. Even if the key in transmission is hacked, the facility of Diffie Hellman key exchange render it useless, since key in transit is of no use without user's private key, which is confined only to the legitimate user. This proposed architecture of three-way mechanism makes it tough for hackers to crack the security system, thereby protecting data stored in cloud.

A mixed homomorphic encryption scheme for secure data storage in cloud [15], discusses about various homomorphic encryption schemes and their applications on various domains. A homomorphic method with byte level homomorphism has been proposed.

A novel technique of cloud security based on hybrid encryption by Blowfish and MD5 [16], proposes a novel parallel cryptographic algorithm, blending and changing from MD5 and Blowfish encryption schemes, which can upgrade security.

An efficient data retrieval approach using blowfish encryption on cloud ciphertext retrieval in cloud computing [17], an efficient ciphertext retrieval technique on a large volume of data is proposed. Initially, an index is generated by Porter stemming. Then the Blowfish algorithm is applied for encryption of files to be outsourced. For authorized access, public key encryption based elliptic curve cryptography (ECC) is used for key generation. When keyword queries are transferred to the cloud, it searches the relevant content associated with the index and retrieves the matching files. Then the Blowfish decryption algorithm is used to get the plain text.

Multi authority attribute-based encryption against data integrity and scalability issues in cloud data services [18], propose a novel privacy-preserving mechanism that supports public auditing on shared data stored in the cloud. Yet, issues such as risks of privacy exposure, scalability in key management, supple access and efficient user revocation, have remained the foremost challenges and achieving fine-grained, cryptographically enforced data access control. In particular, we exploit multi authority attribute-based encryption to compute verification of the data stored in the cloud to audit the correctness of shared data. Through imposing the multi authority-ABE technique our mechanism, the

identity of the attribute on each block in shared data is kept private from public verifiers so, that they can efficiently verify the data integrity without retrieving the entire file. It can also perform multiple auditing tasks simultaneously.

Utilizing Homomorphic Encryption to Implement Secure and Private Medical Cloud Computing [19], present an approach that eliminates data privacy concerns in the public cloud scenario, by utilizing an emerging encryption technique called Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE). The ability of FHE to allow computations without actually observing the data itself makes it an attractive option for certain medical applications. In this paper, we use cardiac health monitoring for our feasibility assessment and demonstrate the advantages and challenges of our approach by utilizing a well-established FHE library called HELib.

Query based computations on encrypted data through homomorphic encryption in cloud computing security [20], a high security encrypted data is proposed using “somewhat” and “fully homomorphic” encryption methods. Cloud service providers (CSP) give privacy and security to the cloud users through cryptographic encryption algorithms. By using query any user can access the data from the cloud servers through decryption. But frequent decryption of cipher text may lead to exploit the integrity and authentication.

Decentralized attribute-based encryption scheme with scalable revocation for sharing data in public cloud servers [21], addresses these three issues by proposing a decentralized ciphertext-policy ABE scheme (CP-DABE) for a large-scale cooperative cloud environment. The scheme reduces the complexity of user secret key management by providing a secure attribute delegation service between a master authority and a number of multiple attribute authorities. The scheme also reduces the complexity of revocation process by using Proxy Re-encryption technique to revoke any users access right. In addition, by comparing with most relative work, the scheme reduces the computational requirements for assigning user rights, encrypting and accessing data files.

Improved cloud security trust on client-side data encryption using HASBE and Blowfish [22], The best approach is encrypting the data on client side before storing it in cloud storage, however, this technique has a much infirmity from the client side in terms of key management, maintenance perspective, etc. Other way could be this kind of security service like Hierarchical Attribute Set Based Encryption, encryption/decryption service if provided by same cloud storage provider, the data negotiating cannot be ruled out since same provider has access to both storage and security service. Customer relationship management for business model that is driven by the type of software as a service method in the cloud.

An Efficient Ciphertext Policy-Attribute Based Encryption for Big Data Access Control in Cloud Computing [23], Ciphertext Policy-Attribute Based Encryption (CP-ABE) is a promising technique to provide both encryption and effective access control. The existing CP-ABE schemes are not apt for big data in cloud since it creates heavy computation overhead. In this paper, we propose an efficient ciphertext policy attribute-based

encryption scheme with less computation overhead in the encryption process by providing the short ciphertext and reducing the decryption time by minimizing the pairing operations required.

H-IBE: Hybrid-identity based encryption approach for cloud security with outsourced revocation [24], a novel hybrid cloud security method is proposed in order to deliver both efficient revocation and enhanced security. This hybrid approach is combination of two well know security techniques such as IBE and ABE. The ABE method is combined with IBE to achieve the strong security against different threats. Along with user identity, his/her attributes like country or kind of subscription he/she has are used for further process of IBE encryption, decryption and revocation. Another problem of efficient identity revocation is further addressed by presenting the outsourcing computation into hybrid IBE (H-IBE) method at server aided settings.

Dynamic Data Slicing in Multi Cloud Storage Using Cryptographic Technique [25], In addition most providers use attribute-based encryption which encrypts only particular database fields which reduces the trust of the many individuals and organizations. The biggest challenge that the present business world faces in multi-cloud storage is that there is no single standard architecture and procedure that can meet the requirements of the individuals and organizations. In order to address this challenge, this paper presents an effective architectural framework with a standard algorithm which would enable to enhance the secure data sharing through dynamic index based cryptographic data slicing.

Encryption as a service for data healthcare cloud security [26], propose a hybrid architecture based on Cryptography as a Service (CaaS) included the private cloud OpenStack platform. This architecture authorizes the cloud clients to be in control of their cryptographic operations and keys that they deploy in the cloud independently of the cloud provider. Firstly, we explore healthcare cloud environment and then we analyze some encryption algorithms. Secondly, we design and implement two cryptography algorithms (homomorphic encryption and RSA) in our proposed architecture for providing security to information based on OpenStack platform.

Secure online encryption with partial data identity outsourcing: An exemplar for cloud computing [27], provide better data access control we have used a strong data security technique in which user's data identification credential and salt is used. Data identification credential, partial element of cipher key, is outsourced to cloud for further use in data decryption process. Decryption process is performed at the user level with the help of salt and one time password. In this system user is kept free from key storage and management task as well as it incorporates advanced and more secured technology of containers to store data in cloud.

E-health care data sharing into the cloud based on deduplication and file hierarchical encryption [28], Quality of the service and security are added advantage to the system. They collect the real time personal information (PHI) and health problems from patients and transmit them to the healthcare provider for the authorized physicians to decide on

the corresponding treatment. They send the PHI in terms of text and image to the cloud, and also the other personal queries related to their medical history. In cloud computing, collected PHI should match the physicians experience to judge the state of the patient and unfortunately, delegating both storage and computation to the untrusted entity would bring a series of security. This is where deduplication comes into play.

Secure Cloud Computing: Communication Protocol for Multithreaded Fully Homomorphic Encryption for Remote Data Processing [29], A significant disadvantage of fully homomorphic encryption is the long periods of time needed to process encrypted data, due to its complex and CPU-intensive arithmetic techniques. In this paper, a communication protocol is developed to ensure authenticity, integrity and privacy of measurement data across a distributed measuring system. The fully homomorphic encryption library LibScarab was extended by integer arithmetics, comparisons, decisions and multithreading to secure data processing. Furthermore, it enhances 32 and 64-bit arithmetic operations, improving them by a higher factor.

Comparative analysis of joint encryption and watermarking algorithms for security of biomedical images [30], presents comparative analysis of various joint encryption and watermarking algorithms of biomedical images to find the best pair of algorithms based on previous research. Comparative results also indicate that joint encryption and watermarking algorithms are suitable for security of biomedical images.

A dynamic searchable encryption scheme for secure cloud server operation reserving multi-keyword ranked search [31], designed a scheme where dynamic operations on data like insert, update and delete are performed by cloud server without decrypting the data. Thus, this scheme not only ensures dynamic operations on data but also provides a secure technique by performing those tasks without decryption. The state-of-the-art methods let the data users retrieve the data, re-encrypt it under the new policy and then send it again to the cloud.

Searchable encryption with pattern matching for securing data on cloud server [32], devised a searchable encryption scheme with pattern matching algorithm for multiple keywords. The scheme is designed with less space complexity and it also provides updating ranked search. We use the property of Trie data structure to reduce both the search and space complexity. Our scheme allows the ranked search with outcomes of most relevant top ranked documents which consists of the query keyword. Because of the Trie structure property, our scheme also deals with the update operation of files or documents flexibly. To ensure the privacy of the scheme, we include the fuzzy search trapdoor and exact search trapdoor here.

Efficient and Secure Data Retrieval Scheme Using Searchable Encryption in Cloud Storage [33], a data retrieval system by using public key encryption system with keyword search, in which the client could test whether or not the file stored in cloud server contains the keyword without leaking the information about the encrypted file. We apply asymmetric pairings to achieve shorter key size scheme in the standard model, and adopt

the dual system encryption technique to reduce the scheme's secure problem to the hard Symmetric External Diffie-Hellman assumption. In the last of paper, we analyse the scheme's efficiency and point out that our scheme is more efficient and secure than some other classical data retrieval models.

Implementing secure data access control for multi-authority cloud storage system using Ciphertext Policy-Attribute based encryption [34], A user is able to decrypt a ciphertext if and only if his attributes satisfy the ciphertext access structure. An important issue of attribute revocation is cumbersome for CP-ABE schemes. This challenging issue is considering by more practical scenarios in which semi-trustable on-line proxy servers are available.

The proposed solution enables the multi-authority to revoke user attributes with minimal effort. This is achieved by uniquely integrating the technique of proxy re-encryption with CP-ABE, and enable the authority to delegate most of laborious tasks to proxy servers. The proposed scheme is provably secure against chosen ciphertext attacks.

Selective encryption and component-oriented deduplication for mobile cloud data computing [35], design and develop a novel Selective Encryption and Component-Oriented Deduplication (SEACOD) application that achieves both fast and effective data encryption and reduction for MCC services. Specifically, SEACOD efficiently deduplicates redundant objects in files, emails, as well as images exploiting object-level components based on their structures. It also effectively reduces the overall encryption overhead on the mobile devices by adaptively applying compression and encryption methods according to the decomposed data types.

Asymmetric encryption based secure and efficient data gathering technique in VANET [36], To overcome this problem, plenty of data gathering techniques have been proposed. None of the technique provides security in the process of gathering of data from vehicles to RSUs. The primary objective of this paper is to propose a secure as well as efficient data gathering technique that provides security and confidentiality to the gathering of data from vehicles to RSUs and vice versa.

Applying homomorphic encryption for securing cloud database [37], propose a technique based on homomorphic scheme to secure this new paradigm. In fact, this approach guarantees data confidentiality and enables users to perform arithmetic operation over encrypted data.

Efficient Decentralized Attribute-Based Encryption with Outsourced Computation for Mobile Cloud Computing [38], present a novel large universe decentralized ABE scheme with outsourced encryption and decryption based on the multi-authority system for mobile cloud computing. In [39], the author presents a novel block design-based key agreement protocol which enables the participation of multiple users depending on the block design. The group sharing model generates different formulas towards generating conference keys for various participants.

In [40], the author proposes an integrated methodology to classify and secure big data which classifies the data based on the risk level as public and confidential. According to the classification, data confidentiality is maintained.

In [41], the author analyzes the weakness in security in cloud environment and analyzes various privacy breach attacks and the methods of handling them. In [42], a knowledge graph-based mitigation scheme is presented which uses and maintains the knowledge in graph manner and evaluate by computing different semantic measures.

In [43], they proposed a novel integrity verification framework towards data security using Ternary Hash Tree (THT) and Replica based Ternary Hash Tree (R-THT) to support public auditing. The method performs Block-level, File-level and Replica-level auditing with tree block ordering, storage block ordering for verifying the data integrity and ensuring data availability in the cloud. In [44], the author proposed a privacy-preserving public auditing protocol for regenerating-code-based cloud storage and claimed it is secure under the considered security model.

In [45], the author presents a novel identity-based PDP protocol to audit efficiently the integrity of group shared data with uploader's privacy-preserving. Due to the inherent structural advantage of identity-based crypto mechanism, our PDP scheme is able to avoid the problem of certificate management. In [46], the author proposes a secure data sharing scheme to ensure the privacy of data owner and the security of the outsourced cloud data. The proposed scheme provides flexible utility of data while solving the privacy and security challenges for data sharing.

3. DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

The proposed adaptive QoS centric service orient dynamic cryptography scheme has been designed to work according to different nature of service and work according to the quality constraints of the environment. To perform this, the method receives the request from the user and identifies the service being claimed. According to the service requested the method generates the reply and the data has been encrypted using the proposed approach.

The method estimates various quality metrics at current state of the environment like throughput, traffic, latency and so on. Around each of the parameters, the method computes Crypto Traffic Class Support (CTCS), Crypto Throughput Class Support (CThCS), Crypto Tamper Class Support (CTaCS) and Crypto Data Class Support (CDCS). Using all these measures, the method computes the sensitivity factor (SF) for the data being accessed.

According to that, the method selects the class of algorithm to be used. Such algorithm from the selected class has been used to split the service data into chunks and performs Class Centric Data Encryption (CCDE) algorithm which generates number of cipher blocks in a dynamic way where for each block of data, the method uses different keys to perform data encryption.

Finally, generated blocks are merged to produce result to the user which can be decrypted by the end user in the reverse manner. The detailed approach is presented in this section.

Fig 1: Architecture of Proposed AQSDC Technique

The functional architecture of proposed AQSDC algorithm has been presented in **Fig 1**, where the functional components are detailed in this section.

3.1 Request Handling

The user request generated has been received here by the request handler. The request handler receives the user request and identifies the service being requested. From the service request, the method identifies the service and estimates various quality constraint crypto support values like Crypto Traffic Class Support (CTCS), Crypto Throughput Class Support (CThCS), Crypto Tamper Class Support (CTaCS) and Crypto Data Class Support (CDCS).

Using the support measures, the method performs QoS centric dynamic cryptography and performs data encryption. Encrypted data has been given to the user which has been decrypted with the user to obtain the original information.

Algorithm:

Given: Request Req

Obtain: Result

Start

Read request Req

Identify the service requested $S_{req} = ServiceRequest \in Req$

Service Data Stat= Access Service (S_{req})

Perform Crypto Class Support Estimation.

Cipher Text =Perform QoS centric Dynamic Encryption (S_{dat}).

Return Cipher Text.

Stop

The working of request handling has been presented in the above pseudo code which receives the user request and estimates different class support on crypto based on which the method perform QoS centric dynamic encryption and generates the cipher text, which has been returned to the user. The user can decrypt the cipher text to get the original results.

3.2 Crypto Class Support Estimation

The selection of cryptography scheme plays vital role in achieving the higher performance. It is necessary to choose the cryptography scheme based on various quality constraints of the environment like throughput, traffic, tampering rate and data class. According to this the method computes the value of Crypto Traffic Class Support (CTCS), Crypto Throughput Class Support (CThCS), Crypto Tamper Class Support (CTaCS) and Crypto Data Class Support (CDCS).

Using all these measures, the method computes the sensitivity factor (SF) for the data being accessed. The value of crypto traffic class support (CTCS) is measured according to the traffic present in the environment and frequency of service being requested.

Similarly, the value of throughput class support (CTHCS) is measured based on throughput of the environment and the service claimed. The value of tamper class support is measured based on the number of tampers occurred on the scheme levels and total requests. Finally, the method computes the data class support based on the type of data and sensitivity of data.

Using all these measures, the method computes the value of sensitivity factor based on which the class of crypto scheme has been identified and a random method is selected from the list. Selected scheme and key have been used to perform data encryption and has been shared with the user in a secure channel.

Algorithm:

Given: Service S, Service Data Sd, Crypto Scheme Set CSS, Service Trace Set STs.

Obtain: Sensitivity Factor SF

Start

Read service data Sd, Crypto Scheme Set CSS, Service Trace STs

Compute Crypto Traffic class Support CTCS.

$$CTCS = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{size(STS)} STS(i).Service == S \ \&\& \ Time == Current \ Time \ Stamp}{\sum_{i=1}^{size(STS)} STS(i).Time == Current \ Time \ Stamp} \times \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{size(STS)} STS(i).Service == S}{size(STS)}$$

Compute Crypto Throughput Class Support CThCS.

$$CThCS = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{size(STs)} STS(i).State == Completed \ \&\& \ STS(i).Time == Current \ Time}{\sum_{i=1}^{size(STs)} STS(i).Time == Current \ Time}$$

Compute Crypto Tamper Class Support CTaCS.

$$CTaCS = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{size(STs)} STS(i).State == Tampered \ \&\& \ Time == Current \ Time}{\sum_{i=1}^{size(STs)} STS(i).Time == Current \ Time}$$

Compute Crypto Data Class Support CDCS.

$$CDCS = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{size(STs)} STS(i).State == Data \ leak \ \&\& \ Time == Current \ Time}{\sum_{i=1}^{size(STs)} STS(i).Time == Current \ Time}$$

Compute Sensitivity Factor SF = $\frac{CTCS}{CThCS} \times \frac{CTaCS}{CDCS}$

Stop

The above discussed algorithm estimates the value different crypto support values on throughput, traffic, data class and tampering which denotes the performance of the environment. So according to them, the method computes the value of sensitivity factor based on which the network QoS constraints can be monitored and suitable scheme can be selected to support the user requirement.

3.3 QoS Centric Dynamic Cryptography and Data Encryption

The QoS centric dynamic cryptography scheme selects the encryption scheme to be used for the data security according to the sensitivity factor computed earlier. According to the sensitivity factor received, the method selects a specific scheme and key from the set available. As the method maintains number of schemes sets and key sets for various class of sensitivity, it is necessary to identify the state of the network and sensitivity right now. So, the method classifies the network state according to sensitivity factor measured. So, the method takes the service data and classifies the network condition according to the sensitivity factor. Based on the class of sensitivity, the method identifies the specific set of scheme and keys. From the sets identified, the method selects a random key for

each block of data generated. As, the method splits the service data into number of blocks of equal size and for each block the method selects the random scheme and key from the set. Using the key and scheme selected for each block of data, the method performs data encryption. Encrypted data has been merged to produce the cipher text which has been send to the receiver.

Algorithm:

Given: Service Data S_d , Scheme set Scs , Key set Ks , Service Taxonomy ST , Sensitivity Factor Sf

Obtain: Cipher Text C_{Text}

Start

 Read S_d , SCS , Ks , ST .

 Find size of data $D_{size} = \text{Size}(S_d)$

 Number of blocks $N_b = \text{Random}(1, D_{size})$

 Data blocks $D_{bl} = \text{Split}(S_d, N_b)$

 Find scheme class of sensitivity factor Sf as $Sc = \text{size}(ST) ST(i).Sensitivity < Sf > i = 1$

 For each block b of data in D_{bl}

 Scheme $s = \text{Random}(1, scs(sc).schemes)$

 Index = $SCS(S).index$

 Key $k = \text{Random}(1, ks(sc).key)$

 Cipher text $CT_b = \text{Encrypt}(b,s,k)$

 Add CT_b to Cipher Text.

 End

 For each block b of data in D_{bl}

 Append index.

 Cipher Text $CT = CT + \#index$.

 End

$CT = CT + N_b + Sc$

Stop

The above discussed algorithm represents how the data encryption with QoS centric dynamic encryption is performed. The method split the data into blocks and for each of them, the method selects a key and scheme using which the data has been encrypted.

The index of the scheme or key has been appended to the end. Such encoded data has been used to perform data decryption.

3.4 Data Decryption

In this stage, the method takes the cipher text and split them using a special character added. Now, using the special character split one, the method identifies the number of block of data which is the last one and the sensitivity class of the data as previous last index. Now, the data has been split into number of blocks using the size obtained at the 3rd index from the last. Now for each block of data, the method identifies the key and scheme using the index values mentioned and perform decryption. Now entire data has been merged to produce the result. The method reduces the overhead as well as improve the security performance in data encryption and decryption.

Algorithm:

Given: Cipher Text CT, Scheme set Scs, Key set ks

Obtain: Original Text OT.

Start

Read CT, Scs, Ks.

Text Array TA[] = Split (CT, "#")

Number of block Nb = TA[last]

Sensitivity Class Sc = TA[Last-1]

Data block Dbl = Split(Ta[1],Nb)

For each block b

 Scheme s = Scs(SC[Ta[i+1]])

 Key k = Kss(Sc[Ta[i+1]])

 OT = OT+Decrypt(b,s,k)

End

Stop

The working of data decryption has been discussed in the above pseudo code which denotes the working of the algorithm clear. The method split the cipher text and split the data into blocks and for each block the method identifies the scheme using the index appended and identifies the key using the same way. Finally, each block has been decrypted using the proposed approach and improves the performance.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed approach has been implemented using advanced java and the performance of the method has been measured and evaluated for different parameters.

The results obtained have been compared with the results of other approaches. The evaluation details considered are presented in **Table 1**.

Table 1: Evaluation Details

Parameters	Value
Tool Used	Python
Number of Users	500
Number of Services	200
Size of Traces	1 million

The details of evaluation being used to measure the performance of proposed algorithm has been presented in **Table 1**. The results obtained have been compared with the results of other approaches. The data set being used for the performance evaluation has been collected from various educational organization where each trace contains various features. Such data set has been used to perform analysis on different security enhancement algorithms.

Table 2: Analysis on Data Security

Performance on Data Security			
	100 Users	205 Users	500 Users
EncryScation	72	74	78
CPDABE	76	79	82
HASBE	79	83	86
HIBE	82	87	89
AQSDC	87	92	96

The performance of methods in achieving higher data security has been measured under the presence of different number of users in the environment. In all the cases, the proposed AQSDC approach has produced higher performance in data security than other approaches.

Fig 2: performance on data security

The performance on data security produced by different algorithms have been measured and compared in **Fig 2**. The proposed AQSDC model has produced higher performance in data security than other approaches in all the cases.

Table 3: Performance analysis on Data Encryption and Decryption

Performance on Data Encryption Decryption			
	50 Services	100 Services	200 Services
EncryScation	72	74	78
CPDABE	74	77	82
HASBE	79	83	86
HIBE	82	87	89
AQSDC	87	92	96

The performance of data encryption and decryption produced by different approaches is measured at the presence of different number of services in the environment. In each case, the proposed AQSDC has produced higher accuracy and performance than other approaches.

Fig 3: Performance on Encryption and Decryption

The data encryption and decryption performance produced by various approaches are measured at the presence of different number of services in the basket and compared with the results of other methods. In each case, the proposed AQSDC has produced higher performance than other approaches.

Table 4: Performance analysis on Throughput

Performance on Throughput			
	100 Items	250 Items	500 Items
EncryScation	67	72	76
CPDABE	72	75	79
HASBE	75	79	82
HIBE	78	83	87
AQSDC	87	92	96

The performance on throughput has been measured and presented in **Table 4**. The proposed AQSDC algorithm has achieved higher throughput performance than other methods.

Fig 5: Performance on throughput

The throughput performance introduced by different algorithms have been measured and presented in Figure 5. The proposed AQSDC algorithm has achieved higher throughput performance than other methods.

5. CONCLUSION

This paper presented an adaptive QoS Centric Service Orient Dynamic Cryptography scheme towards data security in service orient environment. According to the service requested the method generates the reply and the data has been encrypted using the proposed approach. The method estimates Crypto Traffic Class Support (CTCS), Crypto Throughput Class Support (CThCS), Crypto Tamper Class Support (CTaCS) and Crypto Data Class Support (CDCS). Using all these measures, the method computes the sensitivity factor (SF) for the data being accessed. According to that, the method selects

the class of algorithm to be used. Such algorithm from the selected class has been used to split the service data into chunks and performs Class Centric Data Encryption (CCDE) algorithm which generates number of cipher blocks in a dynamic way where for each block of data, the method uses different keys to perform data encryption. Finally, generated blocks are merged to produce result to the user which can be decrypted by the end user in the reverse manner. The method improves the performance in data security and data encryption with less time complexity.

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